

DIRECTIONAL SELECTIVITY AND COLOUR CODING IN THE FROG RETINA

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ABSTRACT

The impulse discharge of ganglion cells was recorded with extracellular micro-electrodes in the excised and opened eye of the common frog, *Rana temporaria*. The responses of different ganglion cell types to a standard moving spot with various spot-background contrasts are described. Information about such stimulus parameters as the size and contrast of a moving object is given by different classes of ganglion cells with preferences for different stimulus features. Of 171 sustained cells with small receptive fields 29 were found directionally selective, i.e. they responded well to movements only in some directions. Experiments with double stimulus fields suggest that this selectivity is due to an amacrine cell-mediated lateral inhibition nonsymmetrically arranged around the centre of the receptive field.

The dichromatic colour vision of the frog is based on partly opponent signals from yellow-sensitive cones and blue-sensitive green rods. These opponent inputs make the ganglion cells respond to blue spots moving against a yellow-green background, irrespective of the relative intensities of the two colours. When the green rods are stimulated with blue light the ganglion cells produce long »on»-responses with significantly lower impulse frequencies than the short cone-mediated responses.

KEY WORDS: RANA; RETINA; NEURAL ANALYZERS; COLOUR PERCEPTION; VISUAL PATHWAYS

INTRODUCTION

The photoreceptor mosaic of a vertebrate retina converts an ever changing light pattern into a correspondingly changing »electrical image,» each receptor hyperpolarizing in proportion to light intensity. The task of the retinal neurones is to analyze this picture by integrating the signals from a large number of receptors.

The bipolar cells receive two kinds of inputs, one directly from a small group of receptors in the centre of their receptive field, and another through the horizontal cells representing a much larger retinal region. A bipolar cell, which hyperpolarizes when stimulated directly by receptors, will depolarize when driven indirectly by horizontal cells, and vice versa (23, 41). This makes the bipolars respond well to moving borders which change the stimulus relation between the centre and the surround of their receptive fields. In a similar way the ganglion cells, the axons of which form the optic nerve, receive direct signals from the bipolar cells but lateral inputs from many amacrine cells often

representing very large retinal areas (5, 40). In amphibians the amacrine-mediated signals are mainly inhibitory (31, 40), but it is possible that some ganglion cells are excited as well through amacrine cells (41). Thus the retina has two laterally operating layers of neurones: the horizontal cells at the level of the receptor-bipolar synapses (the outer plexiform layer) and the amacrine cells at the level of the presynaptic bipolar endings and the ganglion cell dendrites (the inner plexiform layer, see Fig. 1).

As a result of the neuronal integration in the retina the ganglion cells — contrary to the receptors which measure light intensity — give information about more complex stimulus parameters like movements or colour changes. When the ganglion cells of the frog are stimulated with moving objects of various sizes and shapes, they separate naturally into four or five classes according to the operations they perform on the visual image (1, 19, 30). Thus a certain region within the visual field of a frog is described by a large number of ganglion cells (with greatly overlapping receptive fields) representing several differ-

Fig. 1. A scheme showing some of the cell types of the frog's retina (the red rods and double cones are not shown) and the hypothetical synaptic connections discussed in the text. The ribbon synapses of the receptor and bipolar terminals are also shown. The cones are assumed to be directly connected to the bipolars, while the signals from the green rods, which have a wider excitatory receptive field (ERF), are assumed to pass through a specific type of horizontal cell. The signals from the inhibitory receptive field (IRF) are assumed to be mediated by amacrine cells. Some excitatory cone signals probably pass locally through horizontal and/or amacrine cells, but in order to explain the cone-mediated ERF sizes there is no need to assume a wide lateral spread through these cell types. After Bäckström and Reuter (3).

ent types of feature detectors (18, 30). The detector concept as used here implies that certain trigger features are needed for eliciting a strong discharge of impulses, and that the strength of the response is proportional to the degree to which these features are present (for a critical discussion of the detector concept, see 14).

It is evident that the relative degree of excitation of neighbouring ganglion cells with different detector characteristics will give the brain a good description of the events within a certain part of the visual field. Below we will illustrate the detector concept by describing frog ganglion cells responding best to small targets moving in a certain direction. We will also say something about the mechanisms whereby this specificity is achieved.

Discussing the economical representation of sensory messages at successive levels in afferent pathways, Barlow (2) has concluded that fewer and fewer cells are active to-

wards the higher levels, but each cell represents — when strongly excited — an increasingly specific event in the sensory environment. The receptors, bipolars and ganglion cells in the amphibian retina certainly fit this idea. These cells become successively more specific. This simple detector concept does not, however, tell us everything about the information processing of the ganglion cells. It is evident that many ganglion cells have a capacity for responding in different ways depending on stimulus quality. Many mammalian (16) and fish (20, 38, 39) ganglion cells show a maintained spike activity in darkness and when exposed to a steady background and a change within their receptive field may either enhance or interrupt this activity, depending on the quality of the stimulus. A moving object may elicit a high-frequency burst when it is darker than the background but a pause in the maintained activity when it is brighter, and turning on a green spot may excite a ganglion cell, while a red spot interrupts its activity (15, 16, 22, 27).

In this paper we will describe other types of qualitatively different responses to qualitatively different stimuli: many frog ganglion cells respond with short high-frequency discharges when a red or yellow spot is turned on or off but with long low-frequency »on» discharges to blue spots (28, 36). Some observations on other species too suggest that the colour of a stimulus in some cases may be represented not by an activation of a specific type of ganglion cell but by a specific temporal distribution of impulses (7, 26, 43).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Common frogs (*Rana temporaria* L.) from Southern Finland were used. Spike potentials were recorded extracellularly with glass micropipettes (resistance about 20 M Ω) from single ganglion cells in excised and opened eyes (eye diameters 5–8 mm). The eyes were dissected in white light and kept in a cooled chamber at 10–13°C during the experiments. The stimulating light reached the eye through two channels, each with arrangements for inserting colour filters, neutral filters and wedges. One of the channels was used for steady background illumination, the other for various stimuli. Well focused dark and bright spots and straight edges could be projected on the retina and moved in any desired direction. These patterns could be moved in four directions along precise paths and with relatively constant speeds by turning the screws of a hand-driven micromanipulator. For a detailed description of the optical system and the recording technique, see references 10 and 35, and Fig. 2 in this paper.

Fig. 2. The system used for recording ganglion cell responses to a moving spot of variable colour and contrast (except for the carriage system moving the spot the arrangement is the same as that used in the other experiments). The light from a xenon arc reaches the eye through two parallel channels, each with arrangements for inserting heat-absorbing, interference and neutral filters controlling colour and intensity (A and B). Finer intensity adjustments are made with the aid of neutral wedges (A' and B'). Two screens move together on a carriage: a transparent screen with a black spot in channel A and a black screen with a small hole in channel B. The screens are vertically and horizontally adjustable so that the bright spot formed by the hole in channel B and the black spot from channel A can be made to coincide at a desired position on the retina. The carriage moves back and forth by a nut and screw combination driven by a motor (M). The two light-channels are united at a beam-splitting cube, after which the combined beams are projected both on the retina and in a magnified version on a screen visible to the experimenters. The amplified action potentials are led to a loudspeaker (L) and to two oscilloscopes, one for inspecting spike amplitudes and controlling unit isolation, the other for storing responses (cf. Fig. 3 and 7). A micro-switch in the driving equipment triggers the sweep of the storage oscilloscope when the stimulus spot is at a chosen distance from the receptive field of the investigated cell.

In some experiments we used an automatic stimulation system moving a circular spot (diam. 0.35 mm on the retina) with a constant speed (0.13 mm/s) in one direction. This spot was formed by two screens moving together: a transparent screen with a black spot in one of the light channels, and in the other a black screen with a small hole projected on to the retina and forming a bright spot covering the black spot from the first channel (Fig. 2). Since the wavelengths and intensities of the two channels could be regulated independently the spot and its background could have any desired colour and the spot could be either darker or brighter than the background. This optical arrangement demands a great precision in mechanical details. Very small errors

in spot position lead to a situation when the ganglion cells respond to the movement of the screens, although the colour and intensity of the spot are adjusted to be the same as those of the background.

The response elicited by a single run of the spot across the receptive field of a cell was recorded by one sweep on the screen of a storage oscilloscope (Tektronix 5103N). As the amplified spikes were displayed through the z-axis channel each action potential gave rise to a bright spot (at high frequencies the spots tended to fuse). The rows of impulses filling one oscilloscope screen (Fig. 3 and 7) represent responses to otherwise identical runs but with successively increasing spot intensities (see 20).

RESULTS

Responses of different cell classes to a moving spot

In light-adapted conditions the excitatory receptive fields (ERF) of the ganglion cells in *Rana temporaria* increase in size from about 0.1 mm for class 1 cells to 0.3–0.5 mm for class 4 cells (3). When the ERFs of these cell types are stimulated with red or yellow spots affecting the cones, the class 3 cells respond with strong bursts of impulses both when the spot is turned on and when it is turned off. The same is usually true for class 1 and 2 cells, while the class 4 cells respond only at off. Furthermore, there are rare pure »on» cells not included in the above classification (19, 32, 36). The class 1 and 2 cells are very similar and in this paper we treat them as one group (the class 1–2 cells). Unlike the class 3 cells they produce maintained discharges when a small moving spot stops in their ERF, and have thus been named sustained cells (24, 30).

Fig. 3 shows how four ganglion cells representing different classes (1–2, 3, 4 and »on» cells) responded to a circular moving spot measuring 0.35 mm on the retina, which in these eyes corresponded to 8–9 degrees of visual field. Each row of impulses represents a response elicited by a particular spot intensity.

The strategy of these experiments is best described by referring to the class 4 cell and the »on» cell. The spot and the background had the same yellow-green colour. The background intensity was kept constant, while the intensity of the spot was increased between successive sweeps being first much darker than the background (above) and finally much brighter (below). The class 4 or »off» cell responded to the darkening of the receptive field when the dark spot entered and the bright spot left it, while the »on» cell responded to the brightening when the dark spot left and the bright spot entered the receptive field. During one or two sweeps (arrows) the intensity of the spot was so similar to that of the background that the cells did not react at all. It is obvious that the intensity of a moving spot in relation to its background can be well described by a combination of a class 4 cell and a pure »on» cell with largely overlapping receptive fields.

The class 1–2 and 3 cells responded to both decreasing and increasing intensities and

thus both the front and back edges of the moving dark and bright spots elicited discharges. Due to the larger size of its receptive field the class 3 cell responded to the spot used with one continuous firing, i.e. the back edge response started before the front edge left the ERF. The class 1–2 cell, however, had a small ERF producing one burst for the front and another for the back edge. The class 3 cell responded with similar discharges to dark and bright spots, while the class 1–2 cell had a certain »preference» for the dark spot.

The four cell types presented in Fig. 3 together characterize the moving spot fairly well. To take just one example besides the contrast coding mentioned above: as the small ERF of class 1–2 cells is surrounded by an efficient inhibitory field (IRF) these cells responded best to small (prey-sized) moving spots (diam. 0.1–0.2 mm on the retina) and often not at all to large objects (diam. > 1 mm) simultaneously affecting the ERF and wide regions of the IRF. The class 4 cells, on the other hand, which add excitatory signals from a large ERF, responded best to large moving objects and only occasionally with one or a few impulses to small spots (diam. < 0.1 mm). Thus the fact that the moving spot in Fig. 2 elicited good responses from both class 1–2 and class 4 cells defines its size rather precisely (in these experiments we have of course deliberately selected a spot size stimulating all cell types).

The spatial distribution of the inhibitory surround

The ERFs of all ganglion cell types, with the possible exception of some class 4 cells, are surrounded by a wide inhibitory receptive field (IRF) (1, 3, 18, 24). The relative contribution of the IRF is stronger for the class 1–2 cells than for the class 3 and 4 cells. We have studied the spatial distributions of the IRFs by stimulating ganglion cells first with a circular spot (diam. 0.31 mm on the retina) fully covering the ERF and then with double stimuli composed of the same circular spot combined with an arc-shaped field located at a certain distance from the ERF. This arc stimulates the IRF and when the arc and the circular ERF-spot were turned on and off together they gave rise to a reduced number of impulses compared with the impulses elicited by the ERF-spot alone.

Fig. 4 presents the results of an experiment of this type. In order to describe the excita-

Fig. 3. Oscilloscope recordings showing the responses of four ganglion cells of different types (class 1—2, 3, 4 and »on» cells) to a moving spot crossing their receptive fields. The abscissa is time during movement (from left to right), and as the speed was constant (0.133 mm on the retina/sec) a certain time corresponds to a certain distance. Thus the abscissa also gives the spot diameter, i.e. the time (2.63 sec) it took the spot to move a distance corresponding to its own diameter (0.35 mm). The wavelength (553 nm) and intensity (2×10^{10} quanta $\times$ mm $^{-2}$ sec $^{-1}$ reaching the retinal surface) of the background was kept constant. The intensity of the 550 nm spot increased between successive sweeps and was 3.2—4.0 log units lower during the first (above) than during the last spot run (below). When the spot was much darker or brighter than the background its intensity increased in large steps (0.4—1.0 log units), but the intensity steps decreased as the spot intensity approached that of the background, and in a region including 5—10 sweeps in the middle the intensity increased by only 10 or 20 % per step. The arrows mark one (the class 1—2 and 4 cells) or two (the class 3 and »on» cells) spot runs evoking no responses. One whole run including the fast return of the spot (when no response was recorded) lasted about 25 sec. Successive runs started at 60 sec intervals.

tory and inhibitory effects as completely as possible the »on» and »off» responses were recorded at several intensities from the threshold up to an intensity 2.8 logarithmic units above it. Then we added all »on» and »off» impulses (bright spots on the pictures) elicited by each stimulus configuration and used the decrease in impulse number as a measure of inhibition. The distance between the circular spot covering the ERF and the arc was

varied and we can see that the effect of the IRF is strong close to the ERF but gradually declines until it is rather small at a distance of 1.5 mm (cf. 18, 24).

Directional selectivity

About a sixth of all class 1—2 cells in the retina of *Rana temporaria* shows a clear directional selectivity (29 out of 171 cells tested), i.e. they respond well when dark or

Fig. 4. The effect of IRF stimulation. The upper left oscilloscope recording shows the responses of a class 1—2 ganglion cell to 5 sec stimuli with a red (615 nm) spot against a yellow-green background (558 nm interference filter, intensity about 3×10^{11} quanta $\times$ mm⁻² sec⁻¹ reaching the retinal surface). The spot (diam. 0.31 mm on the retina) covers fully the ERF of the cell and is superimposed on the background illuminating most of the retina. The two first sweeps above show the »on» and »off» responses, respectively, when using an intensity close to the threshold. These 1 sec sweeps are triggered at the left edge of the photograph. The 14 following sweeps are the »on» and »off» responses to 7 similar stimuli with intensities increasing successively in steps of 0.4 log units (25 sec intervals between stimulations). With the exception of a few action potentials these 1 sec sweeps include the complete responses. The three remaining oscilloscope pictures show the responses of the same cell to the same stimulus series except that now an arc-shaped field in the IRF is turned on and off together with the central spot. The actual stimulus configurations with increasing distances (0, 0.5 and 1.5 mm on the retina) between the central spot and the arc are drawn to scale below each picture. The diagram below shows the total number of recorded impulses elicited by these and four similar stimulus configurations as a function of distance between the central spot and the arc. All arcs were displaced in a ventral direction from the cell which was found in the dorso-nasal quadrant of the retina. In these experiments we always repeat the stimulation series with the central spot alone after three series with arc stimuli, making sure that the response characteristics of the cell have remained intact.

bright spots or straight edges move in one direction over their receptive field, but not at all, or very little, when the same stimuli move in other directions (Bäckström and Reuter, in preparation; see also 30, 35). This selectivity could be due to an IRF which is not symmetrically arranged around the ERF

centre but on the contrary is exceptionally efficient in one direction (37, 42). As a result of this a moving object entering the ERF from that direction would stimulate a strong inhibition counteracting the subsequent excitation (the time-courses of the responses in a number of experiments of the type shown

Fig. 5. Responses of a directionally selective ganglion cell. The two series of oscilloscope recordings above show the responses to small dark and bright spots crossing the receptive field of the cell in four directions with a speed of 0.3 mm/sec. Each direction is represented by two subsequent responses. Their average number of action potentials is shown within the corresponding direction mark adjacent to the recordings. The diameter of the spots was 0.1 mm on the retina and considering the stray light affecting the dark spot their intensities probably differed about one log unit from that of the background (yellow-green and red lights stimulating the cones were used for the background and the bright spot). The numbers below inserted in various stimulus configurations refer to the total number of impulses elicited by a series of 8 on-off stimulations with successively increasing intensities (cf. the stimulus series in Fig. 4). With the exception of the small 0.11 mm spot at the left, the stimulus configurations are the same as two of the fields shown in Fig. 4, but here the arc adjoining the central spot is turned in four different directions. The 0.11 mm spot elicits almost three times as many action potentials as the ordinary central spot (diam. 0.31 mm) showing that this cell has a small ERF and that already the responses to the central spot are severely reduced by IRF-stimulation. After adding a dorsally turned arc the number of impulses is reduced very little further. As the dorsal arc also extends into caudal and nasal regions this suggests that the IRF is relatively weak in these directions as well. The ventral arc, however, and the caudal and nasal arcs that also extend into a region just ventral to the ERF, all give rise to a significant reduction in impulse number. This points to a strong inhibitory region just ventral to the ERF. After all experiments of this type we check that the observed directional selectivity and non-symmetrical IRF cannot be explained as an effect of the optic disc, a shadow formed by the electrode or some other factor disturbing the stimulus situation around the ERF.

above in Fig. 4 suggest that the surround inhibition appearing as missing impulses reaches the cell with a short delay compared with the excitation and lasts about 0.3–0.4 sec).

Fig. 5 shows one of four similar experiments supporting this hypothesis (the other will be described separately, Bäckström and Reuter, in preparation). This class 1–2 cell was found in the dorso-caudal part of the retina 1 mm from the optic disc and it responded well to dark and bright spots moving into its receptive field from the caudal, nasal and dorsal sides, but when the same spots entered from the ventral side they seldom elicited even a single action potential. A series of stimulations (of the type shown at the left in Fig. 4) with a central spot covering the ERF elicited a total of 24 impulses. When an arc was added just dorsal to the central spot the impulse number was 23, while an arc on the ventral side reduced the number to 14. Thus it is clear that just before entering the ERF from the ventral side the spot passed

through a region with stronger inhibition than when entering from the dorsal side. The difference is not, however, as marked as with a moving spot. This may at least in part be due to the fact that the arc is a much larger and thus a spatially cruder stimulus than the small moving spots, which have a diameter of 0.1 mm on the retina.

All main directions — dorsal, caudal, nasal and ventral — have been represented among the directionally selective ganglion cells studied in our laboratory. The preferred direction of movement is never very narrow. Typically, it includes a sector of about 180 degrees: for the cell described in Fig. 4 it was even wider.

Green rods and colour coding

The dichromatic colour discrimination of the common frog and several other amphibians seems to be based on antagonistic or opponent interactions between signals from yellow-sensitive cones and blue-sensitive green rods (21, 35, 36, 37). The green rod is a recep-

Fig. 6. Oscilloscope recordings showing the responses of a class 1—2 ganglion cell to 5 sec stimuli with a blue (476 nm, above) and a yellow-green (553 nm, below) spot (diam. 0.3 mm on the retina). Both spots were superimposed on a 558 nm background (about 3×10^{11} quanta $\times$ mm $^{-2}$ sec $^{-1}$) and their intensities were 0.4 log units above the thresholds.

tor type found only in amphibians. It shows some cone-like features and, like the blue-sensitive cones of the goldfish, the turtle, the pigeon and the primates, has its highest sensitivity in the violet and blue region of the spectrum (8, 9, 11, 29).

The opponent interaction between the signals from cones and green rods is very clear in the responses of class 4 ganglion cells in the frog. When the cones are stimulated with a green, yellow or red light these ganglion cells behave as described above, i.e. they are silent during the illumination, and possible maintained activity is suppressed, but when the light is turned off they produce a strong discharge. On the other hand, when the green rods are stimulated with violet or blue light, the ganglion cells respond with prolonged »on» responses during the illumination (36).

The class 1—2 cells often show a kind of partial colour-opponent responses: the green rods contribute only to the »on» responses, while the cones contribute to both »on» and »off» (36, and Fig. 6 in this paper). Fig. 7 describes how a cell of this type responds to moving yellow-green and violet spots. Above (A) the stimulation situation is exactly the same as in Fig. 3, i.e. a yellow-green spot of successively increasing intensity moved against a yellow-green background. Thus only the cones were activated. The short high-frequency bursts at the left marked the entrance of the front border of the spot and those at the right the exit of the back border. These bursts are very similar to the cone-mediated responses below in Fig. 6. During

two sweeps (arrows) the intensity (and colour) of the spot was so similar to that of the background that the cell responded with only one spike.

Below (B) the experiment was repeated with a violet spot stimulating the green rods already at low intensities but at higher also than the cones. The relative intensities of the spot and the background were adjusted so that those in the centre of the figure had the same effect on the cones. Thus the cone-mediated responses in Fig. 7 (B) were very similar to those in (A): strong discharges both above and below but no such high-frequency bursts in the matching region. But in addition to these border responses the violet spot produced long low-frequency discharges during the time the spot covered the receptive field. This agrees well with the long green rod-mediated »on» responses shown above in Fig. 6.

As the green rods are more sensitive to violet light than the cones, and much less sensitive to yellow-green, they start »seeing» the violet spot as brighter than the background long before the cones cease seeing it as a dark spot. The response to the darkest spot (first sweep) in Fig. 7 (B) was still very similar to that in (A), but already during the second and third sweeps one can see clear green rod-mediated »on» discharges, the latencies of which shortened with increasing intensity. At a very high spot intensity (last sweep) the green rod-mediated response disappeared again, obviously because of cone-mediated suppression (cf. 36).

Fig. 6 shows that the long low-frequency response elicited by blue and violet light and mediated by green rods differs significantly from the cone-mediated response (28, 36), and from Fig. 7 it is clear that this difference remains within wide intensity ranges. Within the range of normal contrasts (less than ten times darker or brighter than the background) the responses of this cell seemed to contain sufficient information for distinguishing a violet spot from a yellow or green. It is worth pointing out, however, that the responses in Fig. 7 (B) are unique to violet or blue spots only if we assume something about the speed and size of the spot. Very similar responses can be elicited by a small black spot, which suddenly moves into the ERF, then stays there for a few seconds, inducing a low-frequency sustained response to the standing edge, and finally moves out giving rise to a second high-frequency burst.

DISCUSSION

Retinal mechanisms of colour coding

A ganglion cell receiving inputs from two receptor types with different spectral sensitivities can detect a colour border independently of the relative intensities of the two colours because the matching intensities are different for the two receptor types (20). A further condition for detection is, of course, that the two receptor types are not connected in a summing way so that a switch in colour from a wavelength stimulating mainly one of them to another stimulating mainly the other remains undetected as the depolarization of the first receptor is compensated by the hyperpolarization of the other. In the case of the blue-sensitive green rods and yellow-sensitive cones of the frog this type of summation is excluded for two reasons: (1) the different latencies and durations of the inputs from these receptors to the ganglion cells (see Fig. 6) exclude a cancellation; (2) in the cases when the green rod and cone-mediated signals are opponent-coupled the result is a subtraction and not a summation.

A detailed analysis of the cone- and green rod-mediated ganglion cell responses has revealed that their opponent interactions probably are based on an input from bipolar cells, which are hyperpolarized when stimulated directly by the cones and depolarized when driven by a type of horizontal cell receiving signals specifically from green rods (this is assuming that the polarity of the signal does not change when transferred from bipolar to ganglion cells, i.e. that a depolarizing bipolar signal induces a depolarization of a ganglion cell) (3).

Retinal mechanisms of lateral inhibition and directional selectivity

The IRF surrounding the ERF of amphibian ganglion cells is activated by movements and other changes and counteracts the discharges generated by a simultaneous stimulation of the ERF (1, 24). Intra- and extracellular recordings from ganglion and amacrine cells strongly suggest that this laterally spreading inhibition is mediated by amacrine cells (5, 31, 40). Usually the IRF of a class 1—2 ganglion cell seems to surround the ERF on all sides and its strength decreases with increasing distance. It is not, however, wholly symmetrical and a close examination sometimes

Fig. 7. Responses of a class 1—2 ganglion cell to moving yellow-green (A: 550 nm) and violet (B: 435 nm) spots against a yellow-green background (553 nm). See legend to Fig. 3. In a middle region including 6 sweeps the intensity increased by only 10% per step, the arrows in (A) mark two spot runs evoking only one action potential.

reveals irregular pits and humps and non-symmetrical features suggesting that the inhibitory amacrine cells do not form an entirely homogenous network. We think that regions of exceptionally strong inhibition could reflect receptive fields of individual amacrine cells (4). Our hypothesis is that the directional selectivity characterizing some class 1—2 cells is the result of a non-symmetrical IRF based on non-symmetrical inputs from amacrine cells. Calculations based on the duration of the inhibitory effects and the speed of the moving spots used for testing directional selectivity show that only those IRF regions which closely surround or overlap the ERF can be important for the directional selectivity (Bäckström and Reuter, in preparation).

Relations to behaviour

The behaviour of amphibians is relatively simple and stereotyped and thus well suited for comparisons with neurophysiological observations (12). It is, for instance, clear that the dichromatic colour discrimination of the common frog (36), the toad (37) and the salamander (21) correlates well with the colour-opponent responses of their ganglion cells. Dietz's (6) finding that toads detect a violet or blue prey-dummy moving against a grey background irrespective of the relative intensities of dummy and background — although they do not react to green or yellow dummies against a matching grey background — agrees well with the responses of the class 1—2 ganglion cells in the retinas of the toad (37) and the frog (see Fig. 7). It is also clear that frogs and toads do not only detect blue-grey or blue-green edges but they also have a preferential orientation towards blue showing that they »know» what side of the border is blue and what grey or green (13, 33). Muntz (33) has proposed that this ability is due to the rare pure »on» ganglion cells, which have a strong input from blue-sensitive green rods and send their axons to the dorsal anterior thalamus and not to the tectum, to which the other ganglion cell types project. This hypothesis is supported by the finding that thalamic lesions tend to injure the preferential orientation towards blue more than movement detection, while the opposite is true after cutting the fibres to the tectum (25).

If the preferential orientation towards blue is based on the blue-sensitive »on» cells, these units would be true colour-detectors or modulators in the sense of the word used by Granit. Granit (16, 17) demonstrated that besides containing neurones with a broad spectral sensitivity resembling the human luminosity curve (dominators), the retinas of several vertebrates contain units responding more specifically to certain spectral regions (modulators). This finding has been amply confirmed by Donner (8) and Gouras (15) studying the ganglion cells of the pigeon and monkey retinas, respectively.

On the other hand Reuter and Virtanen (36) have suggested that the frog's orientation towards blue could be due — not to a specific detector-type ganglion cell — but to the long low-frequency »on» responses common to all ganglion cell classes when stimulated with blue light. Also the »on» cells projecting to

the tectum respond with long discharges to blue light and short to yellow (32). It is clear, however, that investigations restricted to the retinal level alone cannot clarify whether and how the brain uses the information present in the ganglion cell discharges.

A frog or toad observing a moving prey turns its head and body in the direction of the movement — left or right, upward or downward. Thus the animal not only detects the movement but also its direction. This discrimination could be performed by neurones in the tectum receiving signals from the ganglion cell terminals, assuming that these neurones are selectively excited when the terminals are activated in a certain temporal sequence. The information about direction would, however, by no means be more easily obtained this way than by the above described directional selectivity at the ganglion cell level. Thus it is possible that the ability of frogs and toads to turn into the direction of a moving prey is based on the fact that a certain fraction of their class 1—2 cells shows a very clear directional selectivity. This would offer a parallel to the situation in the rabbit retina, where the information needed for eye movements seems to be provided by specific types of directionally selective ganglion cells (34).

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